

Engage_IoT

Engagements with the Internet of Things

REPORT 3

ADVERT ANALYSIS: IOT PRODUCTS

April 2023

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Summary

[Engage IoT](#) is a research project funded by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (EXPL/SOC-SOC/1375/2021). The core aim of this project is to understand how social actors (producers, consumers, regulators) engage with a new kind of technology (IoT), from the macro level of sociotechnical imaginaries to the micro level of practices of use.

This report summarises the findings of an analysis of IoT products on sale in Portugal. We collected information from shops and shop websites and analysed the promotional discourses according to the type of IoT product (consumer electronics, domestic appliances, security devices, home furnishings, and personal devices) and the main characteristics highlighted: comfort and convenience, customisation, protection and surveillance, aesthetics, health and wellbeing, interconnectivity, efficiency and sustainability, safety and privacy.

Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a range of technologies through which everyday objects are connected to the Internet. Many of these products are aimed at the domestic market, they can be bought and installed not by specialists but by users themselves.

IoT at home raises a series of issues, from the internal social dynamics (who uses the devices, who controls their functioning, who has access to the information they generate) to the safeguard of private spaces (concerns with privacy, control, ownership), from the possibility of data sharing among dwellers to different types of domestic arrangements (families, shared houses) (Coughlan et al 2012). But it also raises the possibility of the imaginaries promoted by IoT manufacturers ending up being quite different from the experience of users (Lupton 2020). And there is a wealth of studies addressing the acceptance/rejection of IoT devices (Aldossari & Sidorova 2020, Wang, McGill & Klobas 2020).

This report is based on fieldwork conducted between October 2022 and March 2023. Team members visited a wide array of shops (electronics stores, supermarkets, DIY retail, discount supermarkets) where IoT devices are sold in the Lisbon region, collected leaflets and advertisements, took photos of displays and gathered information also from the shops' websites. Overall, information on 69 products, of 24 different types, was collected and analysed. The sample is of course not exhaustive, but we sought to as ensure as much diversity as possible in terms of the shops and products analysed. The analysis focused on the characteristics of the products that were highlighted for marketing purposes.

IoT products

There is a wide variety of IoT devices on sale in Portugal. Although some companies specialise in selling and setting up IoT devices at home (domotics or home automation companies, telecommunication providers), users can buy and set them up by themselves from a variety of shops (as well as buy them online from national or international platforms): electronics and home products stores, department stores, DIY stores, supermarkets, discount supermarkets.

IoT devices can be divided in several types: consumer electronics (television, audio systems, voice assistants), domestic appliances (fridges, washing machines, coffee makers, vacuum cleaners), security devices (alarms, video cameras, door bells, locks), home furnishings (lights, window blinds), personal devices (smartwatches, scales, toothbrushes).

Advertising and product information in sales points tend to highlight certain characteristics aimed at making IoT devices desirable for consumers, underlining benefits and downplaying risks. We identified 8 such characteristics: comfort and convenience, customisation, protection and surveillance, aesthetics, health and wellbeing, interconnectivity, efficiency and sustainability, safety and privacy (Table 1).

Table 1 Main characteristics advertised for IoT products

Type of device	#	Comfort and convenience	Customisation	Protection, control, surveillance	Aesthetics	Health and wellbeing	Interconnectivity	Efficiency, sustainability	Safety, privacy, data
Television	1	X							
	2	X			X		X		
	3	X			X				
	4		X						
	5	X			X		X		
Audio systems	1		X		X				
	2	X							
	3	X							
	4	X	X				X		
	5				X				X
Voice assistants	1	X							
	2	X	X						
	3						X		
	4	X			X				
	5				X				
	6	X			X				
	7	X			X				
Video cameras	1	X							
	2	X							
	3	X		X					
	4			X					
	5			X					

Type of device	#	Comfort and convenience	Customisation	Protection, control, surveillance	Aesthetics	Health and wellbeing	Interconnectivity	Efficiency, sustainability	Safety, privacy, data
Doorbell	1			X					
	2			X					
	3	X							
Lock	1	X		X			X		
	2	X		X					
	3			X	X				
Alarm system	1			X			X		
	2	X		X			X		
	3			X					
Movement sensor							X		
Electronic tags				X					
Vacuum cleaner	1	X	X						
	2	X							
	3	X						X	
	4	X	X				X		X
	5	X	X		X				
Washing machine	1	X	X					X	
	2	X	X					X	
	3	X							
Fridge	1		X		X				
	2		X						
	3	X							
Pet feeder		X	X						
Air purifyer						X			

Type of device	#	Comfort and convenience	Customisation	Protection, control, surveillance	Aesthetics	Health and wellbeing	Interconnectivity	Efficiency, sustainability	Safety, privacy, data
Lighting	1		X						
	2	X	X						
	3		X						
	4			X					
	5	X							
	6		X						
	7					X			
Window blinds	1						X		
	2	X							
	3	X							
Thermometer/hygrometer					X				
Electric socket	1			X	X				
	2			X				X	
	3	X							
Toys	1	X							
	2		X						
Smart watch	1	X							
	2					X			
	3	X				X			
	4		X			X			
	5	X							
	6	X				X	X		
	7					X			
	8	X							
	9	X	X	X					

Type of device	#	Comfort and convenience	Customisation	Protection, control, surveillance	Aesthetics	Health and wellbeing	Interconnectivity	Efficiency, sustainability	Safety, privacy, data
Scales	1		X			X			
	2		X			X			
	3		X			X			
Toothbrush			X			X			
Shaving machine			X						

Comfort and convenience

By far the most touted characteristic of IoT products highlighted by marketing discourses is comfort and convenience. Making the user's life easier, more comfortable and saving time and effort are affordances of different kinds of IoT products. These values are applied both to domestic appliances, voice assistants, televisions, or security devices.

Comfort - When we're at home, I always want my children's rooms warm, even if they're far away from the boiler. The wireless models allow you to have a chronothermostat in any room of the house, which means the house is heated evenly.

Choose wisely! [Brand] understands the importance of enjoying life, which is why the new Smart washers offer fast and efficient solutions for saving time and improving quality of life. Dedicate yourself to the things that really matter to you!

With its 1.74" screen, framed to perfection by ultra-narrow bezels, the Smart Watch 2 offers you everything you need and all you have to do is raise your wrist. From workouts to calls, all the options are available to you in an extremely intuitive way.

You'll be able to enjoy the images in all situations, even in the rain and in low light, as it has a night mode that will be able to see up to 10 metres. You'll also be able to communicate with whoever is on the other end, as it has built-in speakers with noise cancellation.

Limpo e esvazio-me sozinho

Evolui para o s9+ para que não tenhas que tocar no pó e na sujidade durante meses a fio, porque esvazia-se automaticamente com a Descarga Automática de Sujidade Clean Base® com saco integrado que não precisa de ser substituído por 60 dias.

Figure 1 Vacuum cleaner that cleans itself

Customisation

The second most frequent attribute awarded to IoT devices is customization, the ability to tailor themselves to the needs and preferences of users. Again, this is a fairly ubiquitous trait, that can be found in advertisements and product information concerning domestic and personal devices. Products promise to know their users and even anticipate their wishes.

The watch that knows you best. To know more about ourselves, we need the best that technology has to offer.

Everything for your smart home! An application [Voice assistant] as individual as you are - design your home of the future.

The Home Connect app allows you to stay connected with your fridge in various ways, all of them useful. For example, you can control your fridge's settings even when you're on holiday by activating Holiday Mode. Good thinking!

Smart lamps allow you to adapt the lighting to each situation. In an instant, you can transform a study room into the setting for a romantic dinner, set the lighting to wake you up or make it look like someone is home when there's no-one there.

Figure 2 Vacuum cleaner that abides by user's preferences

Protection, control, surveillance

Since security devices are a type of IoT products (alarms, video cameras, door bells, locks), it comes as no surprise that providing protection and surveillances is one of the most highlighted characteristics of IoT. However, other IoT products can also be used to ensure the safety of homes (voice assistants, lighting and window blinds that simulates that the house is occupied when it is not).

Protect your home and business without cables - Your home is always protected without cables and at no cost. You can activate and deactivate your alarm wherever you are. You'll be notified of any movement or opening on your smartphone. Depending on the model, you can also see what's happening in your home in real time and record it.

The Doorbell + Wifi Camera is the best way to keep your home safe! It can be used as a doorbell with intercom or as a surveillance camera. You can control your home at any time via your mobile phone. It has a security alarm and the corresponding notification in the APP, in real time.

Detectors - To detect gas leaks / To detect intruders / To control light

Figure 3 Panel on security devices at a DIY shop

Aesthetics

IoT devices are usually on display in homes. Therefore, the aesthetic value of the devices is also often overplayed, both in the case of televisions and audio systems, but also domestic appliances, such as fridges, and personal devices, such as watches.

[Television] Simple yet sophisticated design. A slim bezel and elegant finish work in harmony with the interior to create a better viewing experience.

A true work of art, the elegant 42mm dial catches the light on the curved 3D glass, creating a soft, water-like glow. With its minimalist design and high-gloss finish, the [Smartwatch] is complemented by exquisite straps for a modern, sophisticated look.

The latest generation smart speaker that offers incredible, high-resolution sound in a compact, elegant design. Citation One is very easy to use and perfectly combines the advances of Smart Home, quality audio and impeccable style.

Practical & Minimalist Design. Elegant, Premium and Modern. The new bottom freezer is the epitome of elegance, both in terms of functionality and style. A minimalist design that maximises elegance and convenience. Now you can enjoy comfort and luxury in your own kitchen.

Figure 4 Fridge advertisement in a shop website

Health and wellbeing

Just as in the section above on security devices, there is a range of IoT devices that are directly aimed at promoting health and wellbeing: smartwatches, fitness bands, medical devices, bathroom scales. Thus, health benefits are usually mentioned in the promotion of such devices. The discourses used tend to be highly personalized, emphasizing second person pronouns “you”, “your”.

The band carefully and accurately monitors your sleep patterns. You can find detailed statistics on sleep, light sleep and REM phase on your smartphone to help you understand your sleep quality.

The new [Smartwatch] is the ideal partner for everyday life, always in search of the healthiest version of you, so that we can be better in every aspect of our lives.

Stay motivated thanks to your progress charts. Weight isn't everything. To know what to improve, you need to know your body well and how the different indicators of your health evolve over time through intuitive graphs.

Figure 5 Fitness bracelet advertisement “Do what is best for you”

Interconnectivity

One of the most mentioned barriers to the development of IoT is the proliferation of different brands and systems that are not compatible among each other, each requiring a different app to work properly. Therefore, interconnectivity between systems is an advantage for some IoT products that is advertised. However, this is found only in a limited range of products (televisions, audio systems, alarms).

Multi-space music: The RA3000 can be easily added to a group of speakers in the Google Home app or Amazon Alexa 4 5. Play different music in different rooms or the same music throughout the house with the app or your Assistant speaker.

Thanks to the free iOS or Android mobile app, you can easily manage and interact with another alarm system wherever you are in the world.

The robot is also compatible with Google and Amazon voice assistants.

Figure 6 Smart electric socket in a shop leaflet

Efficiency, sustainability

It should be said that the main function of IoT devices is not to save energy and in fact this technology contributes to the growing use and demand of electricity (Hargreaves et al. 2018). However, some devices can be used to optimise home energy management, namely in terms of heating, lighting and managing solar panels. As such, this characteristic is also present in advertisements and product information.

Good for the environment and your wallet

Savings: "Today I'm coming home later than planned. I change the settings on my devices via my smartphone to delay switching on my heating and save energy." / Savings: "With the consumption meter I can better control my electricity costs"

The motion sensor switches on the light sources automatically when there is movement, so you have light when you need it, without wasting energy. It can also be used in bathrooms.

Eficiência Energética

Com os produtos de automação residencial, não só economizará energia, mas também dinheiro. Compre ligações, lâmpadas inteligentes e controladores de luz para a sua casa e verá como, em muito pouco tempo, terá lucrado com o seu investimento e contribuído para a sustentabilidade ambiental.

Controladores de temperatura Inteligentes

Dispositivos que se adaptam automaticamente às mudanças da sua vida e permitem que economize energia e controle a temperatura facilmente

Iluminação inteligente

Economize energia sem sacrificar a qualidade. Defina horários para ligar / desligar, iluminar cada momento de forma personalizada ou controlar as lâmpadas remotamente.

Ligações Inteligentes

Controle ou programe facilmente os seus dispositivos eletrônicos, em qualquer lugar, com um toque no smartphone ou com o alta voz inteligente compatível.

Figure 7 Energy efficiency information of IoT products in a shop website

Safety, privacy, data

One of the main reason customers state for not owning IoT devices are concerns with privacy and data security (see Report 1 of this project). Counterintuitively, advertisements and product information in stores seldom mentions this issue, maybe to deflect consumer's attention from these problems. Only in a few cases we were able to identify safety guarantees.

The OBL test mark indicates that our products have been intensively examined by an independent testing service provider for logical, functional and technical errors and that information security is guaranteed

Fully protected and secure data stored in Europe [vacuum cleaner].

zigbee
certified
product

works with
Hey Google

Verdadeiros Teamplayers - seguros, flexíveis e compatíveis com muitos dispositivos de outros fabricantes

Graças ao padrão sem fio Zigbee 3.0, Este produto poderá ser integrado noutros sistemas compatíveis ZigBee 3.0. Em qualquer caso, a integração em sistemas de outros fabricantes poderá ser restringida ou excluída, em atenção à concreta configuração do sistema****.

Melhore a sua experiência Smart Home: Os seus produtos Smart Home controlável através da app LIDL ou através de controlo por voz, em conexão com o Gateway da LIDL. Compatível com o Google Assistan***

A marca de teste OBL indica que nossos produtos foram examinados intensamente por um prestador de serviços de teste independente quanto a erros lógicos, funcionais e técnicos e que a segurança da informação está garantida.

Figure 8 Security information of IoT products in a shop website

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